

SUPER i

Deliverable 1.1 SUPER-i Final Guidebook

Exploring financial solutions for investments in energy efficiency requalification in the social housing sector

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Introduction

The deliverable describes the outputs of *Task 1.1, Regional Roundtables*, organised in the three countries hosting the project's pilots: Denmark, Italy and Slovenia.

The roundtable dialogues pursued two main objectives: 1) **building a first network of relevant stakeholders** around the issue of social housing building energy efficiency requalification; 2) **exploring the main financial barriers to investments in energy efficiency requalification in the social housing context**, as well as the **main funding sources** used in the different contexts to support building refurbishment, with particular attention to solutions based on public-private partnerships.

The experiences presented by speakers, the discussions that followed the presentations, and the answers collected through the Mentimeter Surveys constitute the basis for the elaboration of the present document, which outlines an **initial collection of possible solutions to financially support energy efficiency refurbishment** in social houses with a focus on public-private partnerships.

The deliverable is divided in three main sections:

1. Description of Roundtables in SUPER-i pilot sites.

During the events, experiences, business practices and expectations were shared in an effort to support energy efficiency investments in affordable public rental housing. This section describes the discussion held during roundtable events, merging the outputs coming from frontal presentations, discussions, and the involvement of participants through the Mentimeter surveys.

More specifically, the section focuses on the identification of obstacles and barriers to investments, and of the financial instruments and solutions that are considered more useful and accessible for the purpose of requalifying social housing building from the energy efficiency point of view.

2. Insights and Trends

In this section we reported on interesting trends in matters of support to finance, which emerged during the events. We considered as trends either consolidated tendencies (not necessarily virtuous) in terms of funding modalities within a given contexts, or promising emerging practices and solutions which might delineate additional opportunities in terms of funding opportunities and mix.

3. Possible solutions and best practices

Starting from the material collected during the roundtables, in this section we presented the solutions we considered more interesting to financially support energy efficiency refurbishment. This represents only a first step in the SUPER-i project activities, many subsequent deliverables being more specifically dedicated to this subject.

This work will feed the assessment of achievable economic potential of EE investment opportunities in the social housing sector, and more in particular will support the work of T1.3, Evaluation of baseline qualitative and quantitative data; of T1.4, Financial Instruments and Evaluation Methodology; and of the whole WP3, SUPER-i EE financial analysis and investments pipelines.

Roundtables in SUPER-i pilot sites

Roundtable dialogues were held between 26 April and 12 May 2022 in Italy, Slovenia and Denmark, pursuing two main objectives:

1. Engaging at least 30 local relevant stakeholders at regional and national level and initiating a permanent dialogue among them.

The following stakeholders were considered relevant, because of their role and play in energy refurbishment support and funding:

- Financial Institutions
 - a. LFI (Local Financial institutions) and Investors
 - b. IFI (International Financial Institutions: European Investment Bank, Council of Europe Development Bank, European Bank of Reconstruction and Development)
 - c. Public finance institutions (National promotional banks, Regional development banks, National commercial banks)
 - d. Investment funds and crowdfunding platforms
- Social housing managers and social housing associations / organisations
- Public bodies / Local authorities (city councils, regional bodies - including other regions of the same country)
- Energy Efficiency Experts and ESCOs
- Local SMEs in the building and renewable sector
- Local household organisations
- Energy service providers

2. Collecting relevant information regarding EE financing challenges in the social housing market and identify existing financial schemes towards social housing EE refurbishment projects

The roundtables dialogues were designed to pin down **barriers to investments** and to propose **best funding sources** with a focus on public-private partnerships. Besides frontal presentations and plenary discussions, all roundtables foresaw the involvement of participants through Mentimeter surveys. The same questionnaire (included at the end of this document) was presented in all events, with some minor adaptations. The answers collected through surveys together with the speakers' presentations inputs constitute the basis for the elaboration of the present document.

During the events, experiences, business practices and expectations were shared in an effort to support energy efficiency investments in affordable public rental housing.

Roundtable Overview

Italy, Trieste, 26 April 2022

In Italy the event was organised by **CiviESCO**, Energy service company specialised in energy efficiency refurbishment and impact investing, **ATER Trieste**, a social housing company, supported by project partners such as the **University of York** and **APRE** (Italian Agency for the Promotion of European Research).

The event was opened by the regional councillor for infrastructures, and saw the participation of various of stakeholders, such as social housing companies (Federcasa, ATER Trieste, ATER Gorizia, ACER Reggio Emilia), different representative of the financial sector, such as Investment funds (Fondo Housing Sociale FVG, Tendercapital LTD), Financial institutions (CiviBank) and a crowdfunding platform for impact investments (Lita.co); Research organisations (ENEA e ABI Lab, the latter specialised in innovation of the bank sector), and finally representatives from the industrial sector.

The discussion started with presentations by two main social housing sites on which the project SUPER-i will work on, describing **their financial and technical strategic choices** for the refurbishment. Additional presentations focused on **financial instruments and mechanisms**, as well as on considerations on the **societal and ethical aspects of this type of intervention**. They all stressed the importance of stimulating participative and co-designing processes with householder organisations, able to strengthen also **the social and relational fabric of the communities involved**.

Participants: 32, of which:

1. Public bodies: 6
2. Research institutions and Research supporting organisation: 5
3. Social housing companies: 13
4. Household organisation: 1
5. Financial institutions: 3
6. ESCO: 2
7. NGO social housing: 1
8. Technical support to PPP: 1

Slovenia, Ljubljana, 10 May 2022

The Housing Fund of the Republic of Slovenia, Public Fund organised a roundtable meeting in Ljubljana to discuss factors, barriers, and opportunities for energy-efficient renovations of building stock for housing managers and owners.

The event was opened with welcoming remarks from the **director of Slovenia's Housing Fund Črtomir Remec**, while an introduction to the roundtable meeting and SUPER-i project was made by Nina Pečar. This was followed by the presentation of the current renovation project in Trbovlje given by social housing manager Zdenka Juvan (Spekter d.o.o.). The experiences of stakeholders who participated in energy renovations of buildings in Slovenia were presented to support new investments in energy efficiency in buildings. The event aimed to **actively promote Energy-efficient renovations** of affordable public rental housing, which can create a significant societal impact by **reducing energy poverty**.

The round table **brought together all the key players involved in energy efficiency in social housing**. The participants were from Energy Service Companies (Petrol d.d.), Social Housing Companies (*JSS MOL, JSS MOM, NS PIZ*), Financial Institutions (*SID Bank and Eco Fund, Slovenian Environmental Public Fund*), Public Bodies, including local authorities (*Municipality Velenje*), Households Organisations (*Spekter d.o.o., Stanovanjsko podjetje d.o.o.*) and State Authorities (*Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning*).

Participants: 26 of which:

1. Social housing companies: 18
2. Public bodies: 4
3. Financial institutions: 3
4. Energy Service Provider: 1

Denmark, 11 May 2022

The Association of Social Housing Companies, BL, and European Green Cities Network organised in the context of the EU-project SUPER-i, a roundtable meeting in Copenhagen in May 2022 on how to improve financing of investments in energy renovations for social housing companies.

An important conclusion from the Danish Roundtable is that there is a need **to develop and implement a new “ESCO 2.0 Model”** *inspired by the SUPER-i project* and focusing on a holistic approach of ESCO financing of energy savings and building integrated renewable energy investment in social housing residential building renovation.

Mikkel Jungshoved, The Association of Social Housing Companies, BL, and Hans Bjerregaard, European Green Cities, agree that such new ESCO models giving **guarantees on return of the investments** in energy renovation measures of buildings in the social housing sector can play a key role for promoting such investments.

Participants: 33, of which:

1. Public bodies: 1
2. Social housing companies: 9
3. Financial institutions: 8
4. Energy Service Provider: 3
5. ESCO: 3
6. SME: 9

Analysis of Barriers and Obstacles

The following is a synthesis of obstacles, elaborated starting from the results of the Mentimeter surveys held during the Roundtable events, combined with the input provided by speakers and participants to the events (the full text of the survey questionnaire is provided at the end of this document). A more qualitative elaboration will be provided in the following chapters, dedicated to trends and insights as well as to best practices and possible solutions.

Obstacles identified in Italy

Administrative and procedural barriers

- Complexity and lack of clarity regarding the normative and administrative framework, also at the EU level. This comprises possible idiosyncrasies or lack of coordination between the EU regulative framework and national laws, including possible national restrictions.
- Administrative and bureaucratic procedures can represent obstacles, since they may be perceived as heavy and complex, creating difficulty in accessing incentives.

Time-related barriers

- Length of techno-administrative procedures, affecting planning, and execution timeline, including making it difficult to respect time boundaries requested by incentive mechanisms.

Financial barriers

- Financial risk.
- Difficulty in sourcing appropriate funding.

Know-how and information-related barriers

- Lack of qualified labour force.
- Lack of skills in designing and planning the specific intervention, including capacity to understand all technical aspects of possible interventions.

Vision and approach barriers

- Lack of long-term vision and planning capacity.
- Lack of value-oriented approach in the management of public estate buildings.
- Lack of concrete evidence on medium-term gains, which can act as incentives towards citizens or politics.

Stakeholder cooperation related barriers

- Political obstacles or choices.
- Issues related to social housing residents, including ownership fragmentation (some apartments have private owners, which entails different approaches to investments).
- Capacity to co-design with all relevant stakeholders, and to create synergies between resources and territorial stakeholders (enterprises, residents).
- Lack of trust in public-private cooperation.

In Italy 27 persons took part in the Mentimeter survey. We will comment on the results that we considered more relevant, corresponding to the obstacles that were perceived as more important and received more votes.

Restriction and obstacles connected to **legal provisions and administrative procedures** have been pointed out as significant barriers, with 18 votes. These types of barriers cover a wide and varied range of problems, for example legal incongruences between the EU and the national regulation level, the difficulty in identifying suitable fundings and then preparing an adequate application, the complexity of procedures and the length connected to their execution. Finally, respecting time boundaries requested by incentive mechanisms has been considered a difficult task.

In line with what emerged also in the other roundtables, managing the relationship with social housing residents raises some concern (14 votes); in particular, the coexistence in the same buildings of **public-owned and private-owned apartments** is connected to different attitudes and readiness to investments, requiring therefore management and negotiation efforts.

Although the lack of qualified labour force has not been considered a major issue (only 3 votes), qualitative inputs have nonetheless highlighted other **know-how related issues** acting as barriers. For example, the capacity of properly designing and planning the specific intervention, including the capacity to understand all the connected technical aspects, has been pointed out as critical. The **lack of information on green technologies** has not been considered as an issue, collecting just 2 votes.

Obstacles identified in Slovenia

Administrative, procedural, time-related barriers

- Large volume of applications for photovoltaic or solar system subsidies - processing of applications takes time.
- Legal restrictions /administrative procedures.
- Industry standards/norms.

Financial barriers

- Financial risk.
- Innovation costs.

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- Size of investment (too big or too small for financial institutions).
- Uncertain return on investment or too long payback period.
- Lack of dedicated funding sources for energy rehabilitation (e.g. grants).
- The amount of grant made available depends on the type of company that applies for it (e.g. public enterprise, private limited company).
- Energy-efficient building renovations can be expensive and due to the limited amount of financial resources, it is sometimes difficult to decide between renovating existing buildings or building new ones.

Know-how and information-related barriers

- High complexity of implementation as a result of multiple stakeholders involved in these types of interventions.
- Lack of information about green technologies.
- Lack of skilled labour.
- Municipalities lack competences and information to apply for grants.

Vision and approach barriers

- The low prices of district heating (in the municipality of Velenje) were at the basis of a lack of interest in energy renovations.
- The fragmented situation in terms of ownership within buildings, combined with the lack of familiarity and unreceptive attitudes of owners towards existing opportunities, translates into a lack of interest in possible financial services (SID Bank d.d.- national promotional development bank). There is a lack of interest in all types of financial services because of fragmented ownership and the residents' weak consensus to accept the renovation.

Stakeholder cooperation related barriers

- Problems with social housing inhabitants.
- Limited motivations of owners to invest, since energy requalification of buildings does not translate into increased owner's revenues from rental income.
- Ownership fragmentation within the building, combined with the lack of receptiveness from landlords makes it difficult to get enough consents to begin the renovation process.
- Some neighbourhoods have low-income residents who are unable to afford to pay for energy-efficient building renovations.

In Slovenia 23 persons took part in the Mentimeter survey. We will comment on the results that we considered more relevant, corresponding to the obstacles that were perceived as more important and received more votes.

Most participants to the survey converged on identifying as a major obstacle the issue of **financial risk** (19 votes) and the connected uncertainties on the return of investment, including a possible too long payback period (18 votes). Finally, the size of required investments – too big or too small – can represent a possible obstacle for financial institutions. Innovation costs in general have been considered critical by 8 participants. Legal restrictions /administrative procedures have been considered influential by 13 participants.

On the other hand, many have recognized the governance dimension at the level of **social housing inhabitants** as a critical aspect (12) for a number of reasons that have been already explained above.

Other types of obstacles that were proposed for voting were **perceived as less relevant**, such as the lack of skilled labour force (5 votes), the lack of information about green technologies (3 votes), municipalities lack competences and information to apply for grants (4), industry/standard norms (2 votes).

Obstacles identified in Denmark

Administrative and procedural barriers

- Legal restrictions /administrative procedures.
- Industry standards/norms.

Time-related barriers

- Financing of energy measures normally has to be accepted and/or guaranteed by Landsbyggefonden or the local municipality; although this process represents a guarantee for financial institutions issuing loans, there are **two important limitations**: 1) the process takes **long time** (also several years) and significant manpower resources; 2) the loans are limited to what, the municipalities and/or Landsbyggefonden will accept/guarantee.
- Social housing tenants' deliberations in matters of energy refurbishment are usually very slow.

Financial barriers

- Financial risk
- Size of investment is considered too small for financial institutions.
- Uncertain return on investment or too long payback period, being unacceptable for Social housing companies that invest in renovation measures.
- Lack of guarantee on financial investments for energy requalification. Local authorities in many cases give financial guarantees for energy retrofitting measures, but it's not obligatory. This is an obstacle for investors especially in those cases where there is no sufficient real estate value to give sufficient security investments.
- Pensions funds or similar funding sources have limited resources to invest in sustainable development and climate protection, since by public regulation these types of financing sources do not find the right conditions and arrangements to invest in social housing companies' energy saving measures. The pension funds in Denmark represent a major investor in sustainable development, with a focus on increasing investments in the direction of climate protection. At the moment, however, it is difficult for pension funds to invest on energy measures at the level of social housing companies, since each investment is too small to be profitable for them.
- Availability and access to sufficient percentage coverage of loans from Landsbyggefonden.
- Lack of specific funds for energy retrofitting and renewable energy supply.
- Even if energy efficiency investments increase the value of real estate, at the moment financial institutions have very rarely in place mechanisms to take into account this added value when granting loans.
- EU regulation hinders to loans with long lifetime for green real estate loans

Stakeholders cooperation related barriers

- Problems with social housing inhabitants.
- Reluctance of tenants, which are not willing or available to pay extra house rent to save energy and have renewable and sustainable energy supply.

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- ESCO financing is based exclusively on energy saving measures and does not value all connected benefits, such as the increased value of buildings or the improved comfort/health. Tenants and social housing companies tend to perceive just an increase of rent and focus on energy bill payments.

Know-how and information-related barriers

- Lack of information about green technologies.
- Lack of skilled labour.
- Municipalities lack competences and information to apply for grants.

In Denmark 20 persons took part in the Mentimeter survey. We will comment on the results that we considered more relevant, corresponding to the obstacles that were perceived as more important and received more votes.

In Denmark, the role of the Landsbyggefondens is fundamental both on the financial and on the technical point of view. On the one hand, the fund facilitates investments by providing backing and guarantees to investors; however, the excessive length of the procedure, and the conditions applied in terms of what intervention would be guaranteed, represent important limitations.

Financial risk represented an issue for 9 participants, while the size of investments was considered too small for financial institutions (3 votes). The uncertainty on return on investment or long payback period stand out in the Danish social housing system (15 votes), being particularly unacceptable for Social housing companies. Finally, 12 participants pointed out problems connected to social housing inhabitants.

Lack of specific competences or information (e.g. con green technologies) were not represented as particularly sensitive problems, collecting only limited votes (1 to 4 votes).

Analysis of funding sources and instruments

The following is a synthesis of the inputs received during the roundtable events, combining the Mentimeter surveys and the contributions of speakers and participants to the events (the full text of the survey questionnaire is provided at the end of this document). A more qualitative elaboration will be provided in the following chapters, dedicated to trends and insights as well as to best practices and possible solutions.

Funding and Investment scenario in Italy

The sources of funding considered as most effective for energy efficiency investments in Italy remain national funds (14 votes), followed by European funds (8 votes). Crowdfunding and green loans raised only 2 votes each. Amongst the instruments that have been mentioned as effective sources there are:

- Specific incentives offered by the publicly-owned company promoting and supporting renewable energy sources (GSE - Gestore Servizi Energetici) to support public administration, enterprise and private citizens in increasing building energy efficiency and energy production from renewable sources. Such incentives - called "Conto termico" - cover from 40% to 65% of incurred expenses, depending on the nature of interventions, and can be additional to other types of incentives and facilitations.
- National or regional funds.
- Tax credit and bonus.
- Grants.

- It was noted that the intervention of private investors shall be further promoted, as a complementary measure.

The aspects that have been considered more relevant to facilitate investments on energy efficiency technologies in the context of social housing are financial incentives and the capacity to lower financial risks associated with eco-investments through financial institutions support (both with 8 votes).

Besides financial support mechanisms, for social housing companies planning to invest on the energy requalification of buildings, a number of other enabling factors were mentioned as important, such as:

- the possibility to rely on a network of competent actors and of sharing experiences
- the capacity to structure a solid investment project plan
- a set of predetermined and easy procedures
- the possibility to fund activities for the training of residents and tenants, and finally
- the constitution of public-private partnership.

Other enabling aspects were voted during the Mentimeter survey:

- the training of staff on innovative technologies and services (6 votes)
- the suitable interaction between social housing managers and social housing associations, to facilitate social acceptance (6 votes).
- regulation (4 votes).

Funding and Investment scenario in Slovenia

The sources of funding considered as most effective for energy efficiency investments in Slovenia are EU funds (20 votes) followed by national funds (14 votes). Green loans were taken into consideration by 6 participants, while crowdfunding was voted by only 1 person. Sources and instruments that have been mentioned as effective sources are:

- EU and national financing and grants, including cohesion funds
- The combination of grants and loans, including green loans, and through financial engineering instruments.
- Own resources have been mentioned several times, meaning that they can make the difference. In particular, the repurchase from a reserve fund, if own resources are available, has been proposed.
- Credit through the reserve fund (the building common wallet, where each building unit and owner contributes, used to finance improvements and maintenance) and non-refundable grants.

One comment interestingly shifted the attention on the conditions and requirements that shall be associated to such funding sources or instruments, saying that resources that are effective are those **“where impact is required”**.

In terms of financial support instruments for social housing companies planning to invest on the energy requalification of buildings, requests and needs collected mostly focused on the availability of **more dedicated grants from financial institutions, as well as public grants on the national and local level**. With 15 respondents, grants were mentioned 11 times, with different nuances such as government grants, higher share of grants, higher subsidies, larger share of grants for this purpose, state aid. Again, one comment stressed the importance of pairing conditions to these instruments, mentioning **“grants with a requirement to achieve effect”**, implying limits on the effectiveness of subsidy and non-repayable financial mechanisms.

In general, the Slovenian system shows a **strong propension towards grant-based support for energy-efficiency intervention**. In general, the owners of a property develop a energy efficiency intervention/requalification project and submit it to ECO FUND or Petrol to get grants. The rest of the investment is covered with owner's own funds or building reserve funds (buildings' common wallets intended for larger investments in the building). The entire investment has a positive effect in lowering energy costs for tenants, although it still does not entail a sufficient return of investment for the owner, except for maintaining the property's value, because the rent can not be increased - it is regulated by the state.

Other types of arrangements were also mentioned as relevant to facilitate investments on energy efficiency technologies in the context of social housing:

- financial incentives (22 votes)
- the capacity to lower financial risks on eco-investments through financial institutions support (14 votes).
- the availability of more favourable loans, with a higher part of non-refundable resources (grants).
- action at the regulation level collected (8 votes)
- training of staff in innovative technologies and services has not been considered very relevant (3 votes).

Besides financial instruments, a number of other enabling factors and approaches have been mentioned through Mentimeter and the roundtable discussion:

- The importance of combining different funding methods.
- Importance of raising awareness and of receiving specific grants to support related activities.
- Including the owner and tenants.
- Improving the rental policy, so that energy efficiency intervention can become an incentive. This includes ensuring a rent increase after requalification.
- Savings generated by the investments shall be shared between landlords and tenants.
- Provision of assistance in project preparation.

Interaction between social housing managers and social housing associations, to facilitate social acceptance, has been considered relevant (in coherence with the trends described in the previous chapter), with 11 votes. The relationship with tenants shall be curated through specific training and awareness raising activities on how to reduce consumption and on energy renovation benefits.

A general need to further valorise investments in requalification is remarked, through supporting investors, e.g through tax benefit, as well as rewarding owners with benefits for implemented measures and improvements.

Particular importance was given to **the necessity to amend the rules on scoring building/dwellings**, so that the Housing companies who invest in refurbishment of the building can increase the rent after investments. Such an **amendment is necessary to support investors and provide owners with benefits** for the implemented measures and improvements. In fact, currently, the rent of public housing is regulated by the state on the basis of scoring rules where the most important criterion to get points still appears to be the age of the building. Therefore, the time spent to perform renovation negatively impacts on the total final scoring of renovated buildings, since no additional scoring is foreseen for energy efficiency investments made. As a consequence, investments did not show any impact on increasing the Housing fund revenues, which negatively impacts on owners' motivations to invest.

Since 71% of the multi-unit building was built prior to 1985, provided that such scoring rule will change, there is a high opportunity for energy renovation and management of energy-renovated buildings.

Changes in legislation, legal obligations were mentioned as general measures to be pursued.

Funding and Investment scenario in Denmark

In comparison to the other two countries, the Danish scenario is much more projected beyond traditional financing methods such as grants.

The sources of funding considered as most effective for energy efficiency investments in Denmark are the combination of different instruments, namely a financial mix comprising national funds, mortgage, loan and own financing (14 votes). Also, ESCO interventions are considered useful (6 votes), followed by national funds and green loans/bonds (5 votes each). Grant instruments instead have not generally raised the interest of participants, although have been considered useful for the project planning phase.

In terms of financial support instruments to support social housing companies in investing on the energy requalification of social housing buildings:

- The capacity to lower financial risks associated with eco-investments through financial institutions support (12 votes) is taken into the higher consideration, showing the general propension of the Danish system towards investments in this sector.
- the experimentation of new funding models, such as those based on ESCOs or Energy Performance Contract, have been thoroughly discussed.

Other general measures, such as financial incentives (5 votes), financial guarantees (9 votes) and favourable loans (e.g. with a long lifetime), are also reported as useful ways to support a social housing company planning to invest in an energy efficiency refurbishment.

Non-financial instruments or enabling factors and approaches have been less discussed in the Danish roundtables. The importance of regulation aspects (4 votes) has been mentioned, together with the need for an increased know-how of social housing companies (3 votes) and for a stronger interaction between social housing managers and social housing associations, to facilitate social acceptance (3 votes).

Insights and trends

This section describes a number of trends that we extracted from the roundtable outputs. The title of each trend shows in which countries the discussion emerged; therefore, such attribution is not meant to restrict the occurrence of a given trend in a particular country, but to simply show in which roundtables the topic was addressed.

Energy Performance Contracts for Social Housing (All)

Examples of social housing energy requalifications through EPC (Energy Performance Contracts) are implemented in all three SUPER-i pilot countries. Such an approach falls under the more general category of *Pay by Result* funding models, which base their payback capacity on the savings generated by the funded intervention.

In **Italy** this model has been applied by the LEMON partnership¹ realising energy investments for 15.29 million euro, supporting the requalification of 39 buildings and 468 dwellings, 410 of which are public-owned, across 17 municipalities. Investments have combined national funds and incentives (e.g. POR-FESR), municipal funds, ESCOs investments and loans. Owners have also contributed to requalification measures, through their rent increase. In order to do that, the EPC model has been backed up by the development of a parallel supportive measure, the EPTA - Energy Performance Tenancy Agreement. This contractual tool was approved by Municipalities and residents' associations and allows the possibility to raise tenants' rents

based on the energy savings generated by requalification interventions; for tenants the total cost incurred - adding up rent and energy bills - remains anyway lower than before interventions, as shown in the figure.

In **Slovenia**, the same mechanism was applied by Petrol d.d., the largest Slovenian energy company. The company offers many services, including a modern IT solution (Tango) that provides cost-effective planning and an efficient system control and management for smart cities, industry and business users. Currently, they manage more than 335 buildings with "energy-contracting". They offer services for all types of buildings in the public sector and ensure optimal use of energy and water while meeting appropriate user standards. They find the optimal investment solution for energy renovation that suits the client (mostly public or large companies) and takes care of the entire energy renovation process, enabling partners to save time and money.

Also in **Denmark** EPC contracts are used, although it was reported they are not playing an important role. In the framework of our discussion, they were recalled when describing the guarantee provided by Landsbyggefonden to social housing companies towards the financial institutions. Such guarantee would cover any difference between the expected calculated savings and those actually achieved, while operating under an EPC framework (see below, Green guarantee arrangement).

¹ <http://www.lemon-project.eu/>

ESCO advantages and role in supporting energy requalification interventions (DK)

ESCOs are increasingly recognised as central actors concerning the financing of energy efficiency renovations. The experiences reported during SUPER-i roundtables regarding cooperation between ESCOs and social housing companies are interesting under several points of view.

In **Denmark**, ESCOs represent for Social Housing Companies an additional direct funding source, besides Landsbyggefonden (the fund established by social housing companies to finance their building renovation) and Green Guarantee arrangement. In the experience presented, the ESCO company SUSTAIN cooperates with the social housing company Fruehoejgaard on energy renovation. In the case presented, the ESCO is financing 40% of the total energy renovation, resulting in net reduced costs, for rent and energy, of 39 DKK/m² per year.

The Danish experience highlights an interesting aspect related to the relationship between ESCOs and residents. It appears that ESCOs are **trusted** by residents, since it is considered a credible actor, capable of certifying the amount of estimated energy savings and consequently of guaranteeing on return of the investments in energy renovation measures of buildings in the social housing sector. This trust and competence factor has a key role in promoting such investment, since it strengthens the readiness of social housing companies - and of tenants - in directly taking the risks connected to energy efficiency requalifications (for example, it reduces the need to request guarantees on energy saving, or the level of these requested guarantees). All this acts as a relevant motivation leverage for residents on embracing a more energy efficient perspective - remembering that in Denmark social housing companies are cooperative of tenants, representing therefore a vulnerable part of the population from the economic and energy point of view.

ESCO added value also lies on the capacity to **identify and select which specific energy measures** shall be included in building renovation actions; in the Danish case, the selected actual pilot cases in Fruehøjgaard and Himmerland SHC (DK SHC included in the project) will be decisive for which building categories to be included.

An important conclusion from the Danish Roundtable concerns therefore the need to **develop and implement a new “ESCO 2.0 Model” inspired by the SUPER-i project** (which will be developed in detail within **WP3**), **pursuing an holistic approach** in financing energy saving and integrated renewable energy renovation investments in social housing residential buildings where municipalities are mentioned as important possible facilitators.

Green financial instruments (IT, DK)

Energy Efficient Mortgages Initiative

CiviBank, in **Italy**, spoke about mortgages with favourable economic conditions if associated with energy efficiency interventions. The credit options are based on the EEMI label², providing guidelines for buildings' energy efficiency evaluation, as well as EEMI energy performance indicators. In **Denmark**, ordinary mortgage loans are offered, which can supplement the National Building Fund as well as pension funds. Realkredit Danmark described two types of green loans: 1) a loan with a 100% state guarantee and 2) a not supported

² www.energy-efficient-mortgage-label.org

loan, in the traditional fixed-rate mortgages or with variable-rate mortgages (FlexLån® or Cibur6). All loans are expected to follow the EU taxonomy on environmentally sustainable economic activities.

ESG and Green bonds

ESG Bonds and Green Bond are growing in the EU. In 2021, the issuing of ESG bonds and loans registered earnings for €749,8 billion, corresponding to an 89% increase compared to 2020. In particular it is reported how ESG bonds represent 20.2% of all European obligations issued during 2021 (against 9.3% of 2020), while at the global level, 1/3 of total managed funds has an ESG relevance. It is reported that funds with ESG mandate (including common funds and ETF) have generated, in the fourth quarter of 2021, 700 billion dollars more than the fourth trimester of 2020³.

In **Italy**, CiviBank shared their experience in developing its own green, social and sustainability framework⁴ through which issuing debt instruments, including loans or projects with an environmental and/or social objective.

In **Denmark** it was discussed whether there is a need in the bond market for special green bonds that support the green transition in the social housing sector. Green bonds, defined as bonds with a green/climate protection obligation, are not yet a fully developed product in relation to social housing, still requiring a certain amount of leverage in the financial sector in relation to, among other things, the EU's green taxonomy. We report here the point raised by the financial sector taking part in the roundtable:

- The financial sector shows **interest** in supporting energy renovations in the social housing sector. The sector is considered interesting because it is legally governed and because investments are less risky compared with other sectors.
- Questions were raised on the **attractiveness** of the **interest rates** on green bonds for the sector, and whether it is in fact more advantageous to extend the term of a mortgage loan from 30 to 50 years, and particularly in connection with the renovation of the climate screen (roof and walls).
- The development of green bonds could be a prerequisite for the **pension sector** to take effective action in relation to energy renovation of social housing - the pension sector being a major investor in sustainable development in the sector and with a focus of turning their investments in the direction of climate protection.
- The role of policy makers was considered decisive, since it was stated that some **government guarantees** may be required to develop green bonds, and a specific policy demand shall be presented for developing **attractive green bonds** to the social housing sector. In a time of fast raising interests, there may be a need to develop special green loans with a **reasonable interest rate**. If low-cost capital is not available, it can be difficult to carry out renovations in social housing and thus counteract energy poverty.

Green guarantee and energy screenings (DK)

A number of new measures were introduced in 2020 in Denmark to be implemented by the Landsbyggefonden (a revival fund financed by the payments of all Danish social housing companies, to finance their deep renovation activities).

³ source: afme, ESG Finance Report 2021, www.afme.eu

⁴ <https://www.civibank.it/investor-relations/green-social-sustainability-funding-framework>

Green guarantees are a new financial support/guarantee scheme for energy savings and renovation in the social housing sector. The guarantee is provided by Landsbyggefonden towards the social housing company in the context of rehabilitation works conducted under EPC frameworks. Landsbyggefonden will give a guarantee of payments to financial institutions covering the difference between the expected calculated savings and those actually achieved. More specifically, the guarantee will cover up to 60% of the interests Social Housing Companies will have to pay for investments in energy efficiency measures implemented. The guarantee framework amounts to DKK 400 million (about €54 million) and will be active up till 2026. It is expected to move investments for DKK 6 billion.

It is too early to know if the proposed Green guarantee can be effective for financing investments in energy/RES-building measures in social housing. However, it was discussed at the SUPER-i Roundtable that it could be used to secure resident support and ensure more ambitious projects, especially for projects that cannot count on municipal guarantee. It was also suggested that the guarantee shall cover 80% of interest payments instead of 60%.

Crowdfunding for Impact Finance (IT)

An interesting funding model is the combination between **crowdfunding** and **impact finance**, as does LITA.co, the first EU platform for crowdsourcing for impact investing and operating in France, Germany and Italy. Funds are first collected from a large number of supporters through crowdfunding; then they are invested through the principles of impact investing, i.e. intentionally seeking for a social and environmental impact combined with an economic return of investments.

In matters of social housing and energy efficiency, LITA.co has supported the funding of seven projects in France, focused on co-living; green building for low-income residents; green and sustainable energy; energy efficiency in private households. They have also supported in Turin, Italy, the project Homes4all⁵, an innovative start-up and social enterprise aimed at creating a network of private investors to invest on sustainable real estate and social housing solutions as well as on territory valorisation. In particular the company became the operative instrument to address the problem of housing rights and housing emergencies in Turin, promoted also by Turin Municipality. The project mobilised 81 investors (74 individuals + 7 companies) and collected 399.500 euros, over a minimum goal of 100k and a maximum goal of 300k euros.

Beyond technological innovation. Involvement, awareness raising, co-design activities with residents and social innovation (IT)

The experiences presented in Italy offered many sparks to reflect on the importance of involvement and awareness raising of different stakeholders, including residents, as a precondition for acceptance and co-creation of solutions. Such aspects have been taken into consideration both at the level of **project concept design**, and of **impact measurement**.

At the level of **project concept design** we found these experiences:

Finint SGR (international financial bank and asset manager) operates through:

⁵ <https://homes4all.it/?lang=en>

- involvement at the project and management level actors constituting the regional economic and social fabric, in addition to institutional actors.
- actions towards residents, covering economic management tutoring (to prevent indebtedness or lateness in payments), understanding and management of the condominium budget, common spaces management, conflict resolution, as well as sociality-related initiatives in common spaces, also involving local associations, and awareness regarding energy renovation and efficiency.

For Legacoop (national association of household organisations), strengthening community and territory-based relationships is a central means in order to identify partnerships able to support high quality and economically accessible social housing. Also, they stress the importance of involving residents on a large social base and to promote cooperation with and amongst residents, in order to activate social innovation processes in matters of energetic transition. This means pursuing not only technological but also social innovation (e.g. overcoming architectural barriers, promoting electric and shared mobility, installing *case dell'acqua*, social and high-tech fountains for exclusive use of associated residents. These activities have been based on a sociological investigations survey to explore residential wellbeing.

The LEMON project, a partnership in Emilia-Romagna (Italy) comprising four organisations amongst regional development agencies and social housing managers, was implemented in the two cities of Parma and Reggio-Emilia, involving 17 different municipalities in the territory. It represents another example of systemic and social innovation applied to the energy transition and requalification of buildings. In particular, residents have been involved in project design through interviews and questionnaires, while residents committees have been created. Also, a “resident guidebook”⁶ has been created, containing hints and tips for an efficient daily management of energy at home, with a view to reduce consumption and costs.

Also ATER (social housing manager) in Gorizia stressed the importance of cultivating a relationship with residents, favouring their participation and providing correct information, including tackling the cultural and behavioural aspects connected to energy efficiency development and promotion.

As concerns **impact measurement**, Finint SGR (international financial bank and asset manager) bases its intervention on the ESG (Environmental, social and corporate governance) methodology, where the social aspects are taken into account through two specific indicators: Action in favour of the community; Sustainability of condominium costs.

Managing the relationship with residents represents a challenge (All)

In all countries, with the due nuances and differences, challenges and criticalities related to the involvement of owners or tenants have been highlighted as an important aspect to work on.

In **Denmark** two aspects have been highlighted concerning the relationship with residents: **energy and economic vulnerability** of tenants’ social group, and **trust** towards the whole process. As to the first point, social housing companies are in fact tenants’ cooperative, which means that energy saving measures will be financed by tenants themselves, i.e. the most vulnerable social groups from the economic point of view. For this reason, the social housing sector cannot be expected to be frontrunners in the green transition, and a stronger presence from the Danish state is required, ensuring that the necessary renovations are also carried out in a socially sound manner. As to the second point, the lack of trust creates challenges, hampering

⁶ <http://www.lemon-project.eu/p/manuals-and-training-materials.html>

deliberative and democratic processes at the level of residents, for example at the level of project facilitation, project documentation and more in general regarding the whole construction processes. The issue of rent increases is particularly a hot topic, influencing residents' attitude towards renovation measures. In "Fruehøjgaard", a resident survey indicated that 75% of the residents see green sustainability as a priority for the housing association, but at the same time there is a lack of knowledge about opportunities and consequences. It is noted how a better transparency and holistic thinking in terms of cost/benefit would improve residents' disposition towards these interventions; for example, communicating the total costs to be charged, the full set of needs, and the total effects of energy renovations (e.g. reduction of energy bills through renovation), including non-energy benefits and gains.

In **Italy**, in the city of Gorizia, ATER (social housing manager) pointed out the impact of fragmented ownership scenarios in social housing. Buildings with mixed ownership (public and private) represent 48% of the total. In general, the presence of private owners represents an important barrier. Although in presence of fiscal incentives or facilitations, and unless such fiscal incentives reimburse 100% of expenditures, they are generally reluctant in investing in energy renovation interventions, and normally do not approve renovation projects.

Also in **Slovenia** the aspect of fragmented ownership is correlated to residents' weak consensus to accept the renovation, as a consequence of unreceptiveness and "lack of interest in all types of financial services", as described by SID Bank d.d - national promotional development bank. However, resistances also have to be attributed, in some neighbourhoods, to low-income situations, which make residents unable to afford to pay for energy-efficient building renovations.

Possible solutions and best practices

The selection reported in this section reflects the more relevant hints that emerged in the specific context of our first interaction with stakeholders, in the form of three regional roundtables. In parallel, the SUPER-i project is performing additional work on the analysis of relevant technological and financial solutions to support refurbishment in the social housing context, while considering their environmental impact (in particular in WP1 and WP3). Therefore, more information on relevant solutions will be made available by the project in its work in Deliverable 1.3 Report “Evaluation of existing financial schemes”, 2.2 Social Housing EE investments projects initial database, 3.2 Promoting feasibility assessment for the investments pipelines in three SUPER-i countries - final version, and 3.4 Implementation of financial schemes for social housing - final version.

Better transparency and holistic view of the whole process as a way to engage residents and owners

A better transparency and holistic thinking in relation to the total costs to be charged for energy renovation is deemed to positively contribute in improving general residents’ disposition towards energy interventions. Such an approach shall be based on valuing, estimating and measuring the full set of needs to address, the total effects of energy renovations in terms of cost reductions and gains (e.g. reduction of energy bills), as well as intangible benefits of energy efficiency refurbishment (comfort, health, wellbeing). Such an approach can act as an incentive towards all involved actors - citizens, social housing companies, investors, policy makers - by providing evidence on medium-term economic and non-economic gains.

Such an approach - based on a wider notion of value - could help define more adequate scoring or ranking systems for buildings and dwellings, with an impact on the values attributed to buildings and dwellings after the interventions, and an eventual higher motivation of investors and owners. This appeared to be an issue in various countries, and especially in Slovenia, where the only criterion currently used to value building is its construction year.

Towards a holistic ESCO model

There is a growing attention towards the role ESCOs can play in matters of energy efficiency refurbishment; indeed, they can act as funders, as a technical actor - able to analyse and identify the most suitable interventions to be performed, to provide guidance, and to support project design and implementation - as well as facilitators and intermedator amongst different stakeholders and procedures.

In a perspective of trust building and wider engagement of actors, the role of ESCO is highlighted as particularly important. Indeed, it was noted that as much as societal disposition may improve, it is not the social housing sector which could be the frontrunner in the green transition, since it represents the most vulnerable social groups. National support will become essential to ensure that the necessary renovations are also carried out in a socially sound manner. As a support for local authorities and social housing managers, ESCOs are trusted by residents, since they are considered a type of actor that is credible and capable of certifying the amount of estimated savings.

The Danish experience and proposal

Especially in the **Danish** experience, this trend is highlighted as a fruitful alternative for the future, stressing especially that ESCOs, acting as aggregators, can facilitate the attraction of different financing sources - amongst which pension funds.

In Denmark the existing supported financing schemes (Landsbyggefonden) for building renovation include only small elements of energy savings measures connected to basic building renovation, and no RES-building measures. When investing in energy saving/RES building measures in Denmark, the SHCs need **to find funding directly from the market via mortgages or bank loans**.

Considering the scenario above, in Denmark the capacity of ESCOs to provide **additional financing for energy saving/RES building measures in SHC** would be particularly beneficial. This role could be further strengthened with the capacity of ESCOs of **aggregating investments** in energy saving/RES-building measures in the SHC sector, notably **attracting funding from financial sources as pension funds**. These funds are as an example now playing a major role in big RES as offshore wind/PV parks but not in energy saving measures in the housing sector.

The pension sector represents in Denmark a major investor in sustainable development, with a focus on increasing investments in the direction of climate protection. At the moment, however, **it is difficult for pension funds to invest on energy measures in social housing**, since each investment is too small to be profitable for them. ESCOs could play an important role here, helping SHC to **pool forces and aggregate different SHC investments in energy saving measures**, in order to present to pension funds investment packages that are large enough for their action. The proposal is therefore to strengthen arrangements which could facilitate this **intermediation and aggregation approach of ESCOs**.

Developing/testing concepts for “holistic ESCO models” including additional benefits of improving the building components, e.g. windows, and improved comfort/health.

This approach will be tested in the Danish SUPER-i pilot activities, carried out by the Danish ESCO company SUSTAIN together with the SHC Fruehøjgård Boligselskab as pilot host and supported by the SUPER-i partners with specifically tailored advice. SHC Himmerland Boligforening will have a primary role for exploitation. The **pilot aggregator function** will be developed with SUSTAIN as the aggregator and with the pension fund PFA as the potential funding source for the aggregated investments in SHC energy saving/RES building measures.

The ESCO concept to be applied initially on the basis of the following characteristics:

Fixed rate - The interest rate on a financing solution from Sustain and PKA is fixed, which means that the benefit is known throughout the financing period.

Flexible maturity - Financing solutions are offered with a term of up to 30 years, possibly in collaboration with other partners with the same approach to green transition.

Unsecured loans - As a rule, no security must be provided, since the investment is based on the costs of energy optimization being repaid with the money you save on energy.

Guaranteed savings - The ESCO, as a supplier, engages in taking long-term responsibility for the solutions used.

An overall agreement - The SHC only enters one agreement with the ESCO consisting of a construction contract with a financing element - e.g. a loan agreement with general terms and conditions in addition to its construction contract.

An overview of all green possibilities - The ESCO can provide a full scenario about CO2 and energy savings options, presenting them in various scenarios for implementation, including investment scenarios comprising materials and execution.

Implementation guidance and execution - The ESCO will be responsible for the tender process, for applying for funding and for the operation, maintenance and service.

Energy and indoor climate behaviour - Create the best framework for involving residents including indoor climate and energy savings.

Conclusions

Conclusions on barriers and obstacles

All countries stressed the adverse **impact of lengthy and/or complex administrative procedures** on the capacity and willingness of social housing companies to embark into a refurbishment project, often because of the lack of specific skills in designing and planning specific interventions, understanding all their technical aspects and implications, including estimating future energy savings. In particular, in **Italy** it is remarked how the length of procedures, besides affecting planning, and execution timeline, also makes it difficult to act within the strict deadlines related to the incentive mechanisms, with a direct negative effect on the financial side. In **Denmark**, the excessive length of the procedures, together with limitations on the type of interventions covered by a guarantee, represents a relevant barrier.

Another challenge pointed out within all the roundtables is the **relationship between social housing managers and respective residents**, in particular in scenarios of **fragmented ownership**, which entails different readiness or attitudes towards investments. In **Italy**, the coexistence in the same buildings of public-owned and private-owned apartments implicates various attitudes and readiness to investments, requiring therefore management and negotiation efforts. In **Slovenia**, the fragmented situation in terms of ownership within buildings, combined with the lack of familiarity and unreceptive attitudes of owners towards existing opportunities and renovation possibilities, translates into weak consensus and a lack of interest in possible financial services. In **Denmark**, it was reported a general reluctance of tenants, not willing or available to pay extra house rent to save energy and have renewable and sustainable energy supply.

Always in matters of **stakeholders**, in **Italy**, the capacity to **co-design** solutions with all relevant stakeholders and to create synergies between resources and territorial stakeholders (enterprises, residents) was reported as critical/difficult. Contextually, the **lack of trust** in public-private cooperation was also pointed out.

All countries, with some nuances, converged on identifying as a major obstacle the issue of **financial risk** and the connected **uncertainties on the return of investment**, including, as in the case of Slovenia, a possible excessively long payback period. In **Italy**, it was pointed out the difficulty in sourcing appropriate funding. In **Denmark**, it was stressed the importance for the public sector (namely local authorities) to provide financial guarantees for energy retrofitting measures. The lack of guarantees represents an obstacle for investors, especially in those cases where there is no sufficient real estate value to provide sufficient certainty in investments. In Denmark, it was also mentioned the lack of specific funds for energy retrofitting and renewable energy supply.

Both in **Italy** and in **Denmark** the wish for a more **holistic and long-term vision** concerning interventions for energy efficiency was expressed. In particular, it was noted the lack of a value-oriented approach in the management of public estate buildings. In addition, all the **intangible benefits** of energy efficiency refurbishment (comfort, health, wellbeing) are not taken into account and measured or valued in investment procedures, with tenants and social housing companies often focusing only on a possible increase of rents and on the reduction of energy bills. Instead, evidence on medium-term and non-economic gains shall be strengthened, which can act as incentives towards citizens or politics.

Conclusions on most effective financial solutions

In matters of sources of funding considered as most effective for energy efficiency investments, we can summarise the following:

Italy: participants' propension went towards national funds, followed by European funds. Amongst the instruments that have been mentioned as effective sources there are specific incentives issued by the publicly-owned company promoting and supporting renewable energy sources (GSE - Gestore Servizi Energetici) to support public administration, enterprise and private citizens in increasing building energy efficiency and energy production from renewable sources. Such incentives - called "Conto termico" - cover from 40% to 65% of incurred expenses, depending on the nature of interventions, and can be combined with other types of incentives and facilitations.

Slovenia: participants' propension went towards EU and national financing and grants, including cohesion funds. Sources and instruments that have been mentioned as effective are the combination of grants and loans, including green loans. Own resources have been mentioned several times, meaning that they can make the difference. In particular, the repurchase from a reserve fund, if own resources are available, has been proposed.

Denmark: it was proposed, amongst other contributions, the combination of different instruments, namely a financial mix comprising national funds, mortgage, loan and own financing. Also ESCO interventions are considered as useful, followed by national funds and green loans/bonds. Grant instruments instead have not generally raised the interest of participants, although have been considered valuable for the project planning phase.

In regard to possible solutions to **facilitate investments in energy efficiency technologies** in the context of social housing, the capacity to **lower financial risks** associated with eco-investments through financial institutions support was taken into higher consideration in **Denmark**, showing the general propension of the Danish system towards investments in this sector. Also in **Italy** it was reported as a critical factor. In **Slovenia**, requests and needs collected mostly focused on the availability of **more dedicated grants** from financial institutions, as well as public grants on the national and local level. In general, the Slovenian system shows a strong propension towards grant-based support for energy-efficiency intervention.

The importance of **combining and experimenting with new and/ or underutilised funding models**, such as those based on ESCOs or Energy Performance Contract, was stressed especially in the **Danish** roundtable. From our discussions we found that EPC and models based on ESCO funding are being experimented with some differences in all three countries participating in SUPER-i, activating also different **governance settings** - the Italian experience was mostly led by the public sector, while in Slovenia a private actor led the experience. As concerns ESCOs, they express a big potential and advantages, which have been extensively described in the previous paragraphs.

Annex: Mentimeter Survey

Questionnaire presented through Mentimeter

Questions and the order they have been presented to the public might have slightly differed from country to country. The questionnaire foresaw the possibility to provide multiple choices.

1. Your organisation's profile

- Energy Service Companies
- Energy Service Providers
- Social Housing Companies
- Financial Institutions
- Public Bodies, including local authorities
- SMEs (building and renewables sectors)
- Households Organisations
- Research institutions

2. Your involvement in investment in energy efficiency requalification in social housing?

- Involvement in the last 5 years
- Plans to be involved in the next 5 years
- No involvement in the past nor plans to be involved

3. What are the possible benefits (financial, political, social and environmental) of investment in energy efficiency in social housing dwellings?

- lower energy poverty
- increased comfort
- lower energy wastage
- lower environmental impact
- financial savings
- societal engagement in green economy

4. What are the main obstacles to investment in energy efficiency requalification in social housing (1)?

- Lack of information about green technologies
- Lack of skilled labour
- Legal restrictions /administrative procedures
- Problems with social housing inhabitants
- Financial risk

5. What are the main obstacles to investment in energy efficiency requalification in social housing (2)?

- Innovation costs
- Size of investment (too big or too small for financial institutions)
- Uncertain return on investment or too long payback period
- Industry standards/norms

- Municipalities lack competences and information to apply for grants
- 6. Which of these aspects would facilitate investment for energy efficiency technologies for social housing buildings?**
- Financial incentives
 - De-risking of eco-investments via support from financial institutions
 - Regulations
 - Staff training in innovative technologies and services
 - Interaction between social housing managers and social housing associations, to facilitate social acceptance
- 7. In your experience, what are the most effective sources of funding for energy efficiency investments (1)?**
- National funds
 - EU funds
 - Crowdfunding
 - Green loans
- 8. In your experience, what are the most effective sources of funding for energy efficiency investments (2)?** Open question
- 9. What is the best way to financially support a social housing company planning to invest in an energy efficiency requalification?** open question
- 10. How would you support the success of the most environmentally friendly energy efficient technologies in a social housing context?** open question

Survey answers

Italy

Quali sono i possibili benefits (finanziari, politici, sociali e ambientali) dell'investimento sull'efficiamento energetico dell'edilizia reside

23

Quali sono gli ostacoli principali quando si vuole investire in efficienza energetica nell'edilizia residenziale sociale (1)?

24

Quali sono gli ostacoli principali quando si vuole investire in efficientamento energetico nell'edilizia residenziale sociale (2)?

Ostacoli burocratici e finanziari	La progettazione specifica dell'intervento	Tempistiche di esecuzione
Reperimento di finanziamenti idonei	Burocrazia, lentezza lavoro,	Procedure tecnico-amministrative lunghe
difficoltà accesso agli incentivi	Progettazione a lungo termine coinvolgendo tutti gli stakeholder	Procedura complessa difficoltà di coniugare risorse e territorio inteso come residenti e imprese

18

Quali sono gli ostacoli principali quando si vuole investire in efficientamento energetico nell'edilizia residenziale sociale (2)?

Procedure burocratiche pesanti	Problematiche Legali, amministrative e politiche, risorse finanziarie e benefici reali nel medio periodo	Scelte politiche
Difficoltà adozione progetto europeo in relazione alle normative nazionali.	Quadro normativo e amministrativo complesso e poco chiaro	Programmazione/organizzazione/realizzazione/tempistiche
Gestione del patrimonio pubblico con scarso orientamento al valore del bene	Difficoltà nel rispettare i tempi concessi dai meccanismi di incentivazione, e procedure pubblicistiche per l'individuazione del contraente.	La comprensione di tutti gli elementi tecnici degli interventi; talvolta anche la scarsa fiducia nella buona cooperazione pubblico-privato.

18

Nella vostra esperienza quali sono le fonti di finanziamento più efficaci per l'efficientamento energetico? (2)

-

Conto termico 2.0

Fondi GSE

Esperienza è limitata a fonti istituzionali (stato, regione)

Detrazioni fiscali

Contributi a fondo perduto

Fondi regionali

Detrazioni fiscali

Bonus fiscali

10

Nella vostra esperienza quali sono le fonti di finanziamento più efficaci per l'efficientamento energetico? (2)

Incentivare l'intervento degli investimenti privati di natura complementare

10

Il modo migliore di supportare finanziariamente associazioni di case popolari che vogliono investire nell'efficiamento energetico dei loro edifici è

Gestore sociale

Strutturare progetto solido di investimento

Disporre di una rete di soggetti competenti

PPP

Fondi per la formazione degli inquilini

Una procedura semplice e predeterminata

Condivisione esperienze

Come supporteresti il successo della tecnologia più efficiente dal p.v. energetico in un contesto di edilizia residenziale sociale?

Slovenia

What are the possible benefits (financial, political, social and environmental) of investment in energy efficiency in social housing dwellings?

What are the main obstacles to investment in energy efficiency requalification in social housing (1) ?

What are the main obstacles to investment in energy efficiency refurbishment in social housing (2)?

23

Which of these aspects would facilitate investment for energy efficiency technologies for social housing buildings?

23

In your experience, what are the most effective sources of funding for energy efficiency investments (1)?

23

In your experience, what are the most effective sources of funding for energy efficiency investments? (open question)

Grants, green loans	Kombinacija nepovratnih sredstev in ugodnih kreditov	Lastni vir
EU financing, grants	Combinatiin of grants and loan throuhg financial engeeniring instrumnet	Nepovratna sredstva in lastni viri
Nepovratna sredstva, lastni viri	Viri, kjer se zahteva doseganje učinka.	Kohezijska sredstva

15

In your experience, what are the most effective sources of funding for energy efficiency investments? (open question)

Nepovratna sredstva in lastni biri

Nepovratna sredstva in lastni vir

Nepovratna sredstva v kombinaciji s kreditom ali okupom terjatev na rezervni sklad. Če so navoljo lastni viri.

EU financiranje, EKO sklad

EU financiranje

Kredit preko rezervnega skla in nepovratna eko subvencija

15

What is the best way to financially support a social housing company planning to invest in an energy efficiency refurbishment?

Nepovratna sredstva države

Vecji delez nepovratnih sredstev

Pridobitev nepovratnih sredstev, osveščanje

Nepovratna sredstva

Subvencije, povečana najemnina po sanaciji

Nepovratna sredstva

Spodbude najeminske politike

Nepovratna sredstva in povisanje najemnine/ delitev prihranka med lastnika in najemnika

Višje subvencije

18

What is the best way to financially support a social housing company planning to invest in an energy efficiency refurbishment?

Nepovratna sredstva

Vecji delež nepovratnih sredstev za ta namen.

Nepovratna sredstva z zahtevo po doseganju učinka.

Kombinacija ukrepov ter ozaveščanje, pomoč pri pripravi projektov

nepovratna sredstva , pomoč države

Financne vzpodbude

Best way is to combine grants and include owners or / and tenants

Ugodnejša posojila, višji del nepovratnih sredstev

Ugodnejše posojilo, višji del nepovratnih sredstev, dodatna sredstva za osveščanje

How would you support the success of the most environmentally friendly energy efficient technologies in a social housing context?

subvencije, pomoč države, sprememba zakonodaje

Zakonske obveze

Visje subvencije

S spremembo Pravilnika o tockovanju stanovanj, ki bi omogočil dvig najemnine po izvedeni investiciji .

Vec sredstev za ta name

Ugodnejša posojila, večji del nepovratnih sredstev, dodatna sredstva za osveščanje, olajšave

Potrebno je podpreti investitorje in lastnikom omogočiti ugodnosti za izvedene ukrepe ter izboljšave.

Davčne ugodnosti investitorjem

Zagotavljanje javne infrastrukture obnovljivih virov

Acronyms

EE: Energy Efficiency

EU: European Union

FI: Financial Institutions

PV: Photovoltaic

SHC: Social Housing Company

RE: Renewable Energy

RES: Renewable Energy Sources